

NEURAL MACHINE TRANSLATION OF AZERBAIJANI SENTENCES

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Master in Computer Engineering, Baku, Azerbaijan***ABSTRACT**

Today, the advancements in technology, increased computational power and massive amounts of data have been playing crucial role in the realms of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML). The advancements in these fields in turn, plays an important role in multiple sectors. As these technologies have evolved rapidly, they become offering new capabilities that were impossible before. Apart from the other areas, these advancements and innovations in technology are reflected in machine translation methods. The main goal of this work is to apply state of the art techniques and methodologies in order to solve machine translation problem for Azerbaijani language. The purpose of this project is to use latest deep learning models in real world applications such as language translators. Using the latest innovations and state-of-the-art techniques of artificial intelligence has led to significant improvements in accuracy, quality, and efficiency across various applications, from natural language processing and image recognition to predictive analytics and personalized recommendations, transforming industries and enhancing user experiences.

Keywords: deep learning, machine translation, sequence-to-sequence model, attention mechanism, encoder-decoder, transformers, neural machine translation.

1. Introduction

In most of the discussions about AI, the term artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning are utilized synonymously.

Machine learning is one of the fields in artificial intelligence which involves creating and building statistical models [1]. Machine learning algorithms leverage data in order to identify patterns in data and extract meaning out of it. These models can improve their performance by using methods such as hyperparameter tuning, improvement of the datasets, feature engineering, and the application of more advanced or specialized machine learning algorithms, ensuring they become more efficient, accurate, and capable of handling complex tasks over time [2]. One of the key principles of machine learning algorithms is that they perform predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed [3].

With the increase in the massive amounts of data produced every day, extracting knowledge using traditional machine learning algorithms are often goes beyond their limits. In order to process this large amounts of data, complex deep learning based models are proposed. Deep learning is one of the subfields of machine learning which is based on artificial neural networks. Deep learning itself is comprised of many different architectures, such as feedforward neural networks, convolutional neural networks (CNN), recurrent neural networks (RNN), and transformers [4]. These architectures have proven themselves in many different areas such as natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, speech recognition, biology, medical science, climate science, machine translation and so on. Inspiration of artificial neural networks comes from biological systems. Basically, biological neural networks consisting of neurons linked through synapses, a single neuron has the capability to form connections with thousands

of others, creating an intricate network. Neurons interact through electrochemical signals, where synapses adjust the intensity of these communications [5]. However, in artificial neural networks learning takes place via algorithms that modify the connection weights in response to the discrepancy between predicted outcomes and actual results. Methods such as backpropagation are prime examples of this learning mechanism.

Machine translation consists of several approaches to translate speech or text from one language to another while preserving the overall meaning of the sentence. These approaches vary on the basis of their underlying technologies, such as rule-based, statistical, neural, and hybrid models, each with its strengths and limitations depending on the complexity of the language, the context of the conversation, and the specific requirements of the translation task [6, 7]. Machine translation using machine learning approach involves automatic translation of text from one language to the another without any human participation.

Recent methodologies for machine translation goes surpass simple word-to-word translation and considers contextual information. Here are the major benefits of machine translation [8].

1. Improved speed and efficiency.
2. Cost effectiveness.
3. Accessibility and Inclusivity.
4. Business and Commerce.

In their research study, Saini and Sahula examined different techniques and approaches for machine translation for several Indian languages. They examined different approaches such as hybrid machine translation, rule-based translation, corpus-based translation, finding that each method has its unique advantages and challenges [6]. Lipton and Berkowitz investigated state of the art methods for sequence learning in which they come up with important information for neural machine

translation [9]. In another research, Yang et al. examined different techniques for neural machine translation, including sequence-to-sequence models, attention mechanisms, and transformer models, demonstrating how each technique contributes to improving the fluency, accuracy, and speed of translations by effectively capturing the nuances of language and context [7].

Neural Machine Translation (NMT) has emerged as a major advancement over traditional statistical machine translation (SMT) techniques, providing improvements in translation quality, operational efficiency, and system adaptability. Thanks to its ability to process and learn from an expansive corpus of text, NMT continuously refines its translation capabilities.

2. Statement of the Problem

Neural Machine Translation (NMT) is considered as the revolutionary approach in the field of automated language translation. In this approach we use different deep learning algorithms in order to translate sentences from one language into another [10]. While this approach brings significant improvements to the industry, languages such as Azerbaijani brings unique challenges due to its complexity of its linguistic structure. Addressing these challenges will bring new opportunities to enhance global communication, improve more accurate and accessible information exchange, and drive innovation in artificial intelligence and computational linguistics. By improving neural machine translation of Azerbaijani sentences, researchers and technologists can bridge linguistic divides, making educational and professional content more universally accessible. This advancement will not only benefit the field of machine learning but also have profound implications for international commerce, education, and cultural exchange, bringing opportunities for a more interconnected and mutually understanding global society.

Azerbaijani is an agglutinative language. This means that in this language, we form words and express grammatical relationships through the addition of prefixes and suffixes. This morphological richness presents a significant challenge for neural machine translation systems, which means that we must parse and generate long sequences of morphemes accurately. In addition, Azerbaijani's contextual nuances demand a deep understanding of syntax and semantics. This also further complicates the translation process.

One of the main obstacles in neural machine translation (NMT) of Azerbaijani sentences is the scarcity of high-quality, diverse parallel corpora. The availability of large, annotated datasets is crucial for training effective NMT models [11, 12]. However, for this language, we lack extensive bilingual corpora, especially in specialized or specific domains. This also limits the models' ability to learn and accurately translate complex sentences.

Despite the fact that there has been considerable progress in NMT, there are still several gaps remain, particularly in translation of less common language pairs [13]. In the fields and domains where terminology and stylistic nuances are critical, there is a massive need to enhance translation accuracy and fluency. For example, accurate and effective translation is very important in education systems. In the research study of Chauhan

and Daniel, they investigated different evaluation methods [14]. For their study, they classified evaluation metrics into five categories such as lexical, character, semantic, syntactic, and semantic & syntactic. Furthermore, existing research needs to fully address the integration of feedback mechanisms that allow NMT systems to learn continuously from corrections and adapt over time, which is improving their performance.

The central problem this research aims to address is the accurate translation of nuanced Azerbaijani sentences, without compromising contextual integrity. This in turn, involves not only technical challenge of developing more sophisticated translation models, but at the same time ensuring that the models can adapt to details that are represented in various contexts.

3. Solution Method

Machine translation has evolved steadily since its beginning. Early translation systems are often relied on rule-based techniques in which, determined linguistic rules and mappings are applied for translation. However, as we know, human language is complex and it varies greatly from one community to another, often filled with nuances, idioms, and cultural references that can be challenging for even the most advanced translation systems to grasp it accurately. Statistical machine translation (SMT) methods provided significant leap over traditional, rule-based methods. SMT systems have learned to translate sentences by examining large number of bilingual text data, but they still encountered challenges on different expressions, nuances and maintaining overall contextual meaning over longer textual data.

In order to solve these problems, neural machine translation (NMT) methods have been introduced. NMT represented a significant leap forward over the traditional and SMT based methods. They become incredibly popular due to their effectiveness. In particular, NMT uses complex deep learning models such as recurrent neural networks or transformer-based models to learn the details of the language from large amounts of text corpora.

The architecture of the network is crucial aspect for the performance of the NMT systems. In this work we use transformer-based network architecture that has two main components: encoder and decoder [15]. Encoder component reads input sentence and transforms it to the intermediate format [16]. After that, decoder component reads the data that is in intermediate format and outputs translation for the given sentence [16]. In each component we also have attention mechanism that helps to create representations that are influenced by the surrounding context [15].

The quality of the data is essential for the effectiveness of the neural machine translation model. In order to train NMT model we must first collect the data. Data may not always be in perfect shape, but we can further apply some preprocessing techniques to create dataset which is usable for training. In this research, the dataset undergoes cleaning to remove any corrupt or irrelevant content. After that, normalization techniques are being applied which includes converting all text to lowercase and removing punctuation and ensuring overall consistency across the dataset. Like the other

learning algorithms, machine translation algorithms also cannot process data in raw text format. In order to use our dataset to train the model, we must first find a way to represent our textual data in a format so that learning algorithms can be trained on. On literature this process is called tokenization. In tokenization process, the sentences are split into individual tokens and these tokens are represented by numbers. In our research we used several datasets to train our machine translation model. In particular, our experiment is conducted using

on two different base models. Dataset that we will use is TED2020 dataset. The models that we will use are opus-mt-az-en and mt5-base model. These models are pretrained on vast amounts of data, and we finetuned them for our specific need, which is translation of the text from one language to another. In our experiments, we trained our first model for 20 epochs. Figure 1 shows training and validation loss curve for the first model.

Figure 1

As we see from the graph, our first model is starting to overfit to the training dataset. Apart from that, our second model is trained for 30 epochs and Figure 2 shows training and validation loss for the trained model.

Figure 2

According to the Figure 2, we can clearly see that for later epochs the loss is starting to decrease slowly. But we can further train our model for longer epochs and compare the results.

4. Conclusion

In this research we experimented with two different Neural Machine Translation (NMT) models. Also, we emphasized the challenges and opportunities pre-

sented by the linguistic characteristics of the Azerbaijani language. Through the implementation of an advanced encoder-decoder architecture complemented by an attention mechanism, we have demonstrated the training and validation loss curves for our trained models.

According to our findings the preprocessing steps, such as normalization of input text and the tokenization process were one of the key elements in enhancing

model's ability on translating different linguistic features. Additionally, the application of the attention mechanism paved the way for our model to capture contextual details which results not only accurate, but contextually applicable translations.

However, the performance of the model depends on several factors. For example, obtaining high quality and large datasets are one of the keys for the deep learning models to demonstrate their powers. Our first model was trained on different dataset and it was already achieving applicable results even after first couple epochs. On the other hand, our second model was general purpose model and we took it and finetuned it for our machine translation purposes. For the continuation, we can further update our dataset and train our model for much longer epochs.

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the potential of NMT which revolutionizes the translation of sentences, providing a foundation upon which future research can build to further enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and applicability of machine translation technologies.

References

1. IBM. What is machine learning? Available at: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/machine-learning>.
2. Manjula C. Belavagi, Balachandra Muniyal. (2016). Performance Evaluation of Supervised Machine Learning Algorithms for Intrusion Detection. *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 89. (pp. 117-123).
3. Machine learning, explained. Available at: <https://mitsloan.mit.edu/ideas-made-to-matter/machine-learning-explained>.
4. Pouyanfar, S., Sadiq, S., Yan, Y., Tian, H., Tao, Y., Reyes, M. P., ... & Iyengar, S. S. (2018). A survey on deep learning: Algorithms, techniques, and applications. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 51(5), 1-36.
5. Kriegeskorte, N., & Golan, T. (2019). Neural network models and deep learning. *Current Biology*, 29(7), R231-R236.
6. Saini, S., & Sahula, V. (2015, February). A survey of machine translation techniques and systems for Indian languages. In 2015 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence & Communication Technology (pp. 676-681). IEEE.
7. Yang, S., Wang, Y., & Chu, X. (2020). A survey of deep learning techniques for neural machine translation. arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.07526.
8. What is Machine Translation? – Neural Machine Translation Explained – AWS. Available at: <https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/machine-translation/>.
9. Lipton, Z. C., Berkowitz, J., & Elkan, C. (2015). A critical review of recurrent neural networks for sequence learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:1506.00019.
10. Wu, Y., Schuster, M., Chen, Z., Le, Q. V., Noorouzi, M., Macherey, W., ... & Dean, J. (2016). Google's neural machine translation system: Bridging the gap between human and machine translation. arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.08144.
11. Halevy, A., Norvig, P., & Pereira, F. (2009). The unreasonable effectiveness of data. *IEEE intelligent systems*, 24(2), 8-12.
12. Sun, C., Shrivastava, A., Singh, S., & Gupta, A. (2017). Revisiting unreasonable effectiveness of data in deep learning era. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision* (pp. 843-852).
13. Zhang, J., & Zong, C. (2020). Neural machine translation: Challenges, progress and future. *Science China Technological Sciences*, 63(10), 2028-2050.
14. Chauhan, S., Daniel, P. (2023). A Comprehensive Survey on Various Fully Automatic Machine Translation Evaluation Metrics. *Neural Process Lett* 55, 12663–12717.
15. Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., ... & Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is all you need. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 30.
16. Cho, K., Van Merriënboer, B., Gulcehre, C., Bahdanau, D., Bougares, F., Schwenk, H., & Bengio, Y. (2014). Learning phrase representations using RNN encoder-decoder for statistical machine translation. arXiv preprint arXiv:1406.1078.